

EFFECT OF FACILITATED TUCKING AND NON-NUTRITIVE SUCKING ON PAIN INTENSITY AMONG PRETERM INFANTS DURING HEEL-STICK

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Abstract

Background: Pain management by non-pharmacological interventions in neonates is a crucial area of research. **Aim:** To evaluate the effect of facilitated tucking and non-nutritive sucking on pain intensity among preterm infants during heel-stick. **Methods:** A quasi –experimental research pre-posttest design was utilized on a purposive sample of one hundred and twenty one preterm infants from Neonatal Intensive Care Units at El Manial (Kaser Al Aini) and EL Monira Pediatric Hospitals that are affiliated to Cairo University from April 2023 to July 2024. They were allocated into four groups (control /no pain relief method, facilitated tucking, non-nutritive sucking, and facilitated tucking combined with non-nutritive sucking). Facilitated tucking, non-nutritive sucking, and facilitated tucking combined with non-nutritive sucking were compared with the routine care method (no intervention) of heel stick and pain was measured two times for each method before heel stick (baseline), and during heel stick (with intervention). The pain score was measured by the Premature Infant Pain Profile (PIPP). Results: The pain score during heel stick was significantly lowered with using facilitated tucking combined with non-nutritive sucking (4.87 ± 2.583), facilitated tucking (6.68 ± 2.344) and non-nutritive sucking (9.67 ± 3.100) in comparison to the routine care method (11.57 ± 3.510) of heel stick ($P = .000$). Combination of facilitated tucking with non-nutritive sucking was more effective than facilitated tucking or non-nutritive sucking ($P = .000$). **Conclusion:** Combination of facilitated tucking with non-nutritive sucking followed by facilitated tucking and non-nutritive sucking were effectively reduced pain scores more than routine care during heel-stick procedure. Combination of facilitated tucking with non-nutritive sucking is the most effective intervention that reduced PIPP scores among preterm infants during heel stick procedure. **Recommendation:** This study can be replicated on a large group of sample to validate the findings and to make generalizations and it can be taking up on other procedural pain that occur in neonatal intensive care units.

Keywords: Preterm Infant, Pain, FT, Non- Nutritive Sucking.

1. INTRODUCTION

World Health Organization (WHO), defined preterm as neonate had born alive before 37 weeks of pregnancy are completed [1]. Preterm birth is a significant global health issue, every year; an estimated 15 million neonates are born preterm that is more than 1 in 10 neonates [2]. In case of premature birth, the preterm infant is placed in an unfavorable environment in the Neonatal Intensive Care Unit (NICU); which is a place full of light, noise, and stress [3]. Preterm infants in NICU are exposed to pain at levels ranging from

trivial to severe such as heel stick, venipuncture, vitamin K injection, intramuscular (IM) vaccination or suctioning [4].

Pain has been defined by the International Association for the Study of Pain ([IASP], as an unpleasant sensory and emotional experience associated with actual or potential tissue damage or described in terms of such damage [5]. Preterm infants are at the greatest risk of neurodevelopment impairment as a result of preterm birth and painful stimuli in NICUs. In several studies, preterm infant had a mean of 10 to 15 painful procedures per day during their first two days of life; heel sticks and suctioning are the most common types of pain experienced in the NICU and may be associated with impaired physiological, neurologic and immunologic functioning [6].

Pain management for preterm infants in the NICU reflects unique challenges, as repeated exposure to painful procedures which cause immediate and long-term developmental impacts on preterm infants [7]. Pharmacological management for pain relief is associated with possible risks and side effects, so non-pharmacological interventions are increasingly prioritized to manage pain in neonatal care settings such as Facilitated Tucking (FT), Non-Nutritive Sucking (NNS), swaddling, changing position, massage, and breastfeeding which are aimed to prevent the intensification of a painful process, the disorganization, the stress and the agitation of the newborn, thus minimizing the effect of pain. Non-pharmacological treatment methods are being increasingly discussed with regard to pain prevention and relief either alone or in combination with pharmacological treatment [8].

Facilitated Tucking (FT) is one of the simplest non-pharmacological and cost-effective techniques simulating the condition of being in the uterus. Thereafter, the preterm is positioned in a flexed midline position in either side-lying, supine or prone positions which assist a preterm ability to use own self-regulatory skills, such as hands to mouth for grasping or holding, so that the preterm can better cope with pain and stress [9]. FT makes the preterm comfortable, and more secure with a controlled response. FT facilitates self-regulation by decreasing the physiologic response like prolonged heart rate elevation that contributes to the disequilibrium associated with pain and stress. Also FT improves emotional security and reduces the pain response [10].

A systematic review and meta-analysis was done under the title “The effect of facilitated tucking position during the painful procedure in pain management of preterm infants in neonatal intensive care unit” included fifteen studies met the eligibility criteria, including 664 preterm infants concluded that FT position can improve the pain relief during painful procedures [9]. Also, another Cochrane systematic review and meta-analysis examining the pain-reducing effect of FT [11] demonstrated that term and preterm infants who received FT had reduced pain response immediately following painful procedures.

Non-Nutritive Sucking (NNS) is a foundational skill of infancy and a primitive reflex that is a predictable, rhythmical and involuntary response elicited when a tactile input is given in or around the mouth, resulting in the infant closing the mouth around the stimulus, developing an intraoral pressure system, and engaging in rhythmical compression and

suction on the stimulus that is important for oral feeding and self-regulation [12]. A Cochrane systematic review and meta-analysis of non-pharmacological interventions for newborn procedural pain demonstrated that NNS improved regulation following painful procedures in both full-term and preterm neonates, and also improved pain reactivity in full-term neonates [11].

2. METHODS

2.1 Aim

To evaluate the effect of facilitated tucking and non-nutritive sucking on pain intensity among preterm infants during heel-stick. To achieve the aim of the current study the following research hypotheses were postulated:

H₁: Mean pain scores will be lowered among preterm infants' who will receive FT and/ or NNS during heel stick procedure than control.

H₂: Mean pain scores will be lowered among preterm infants' who will receive FT combined with NNS than who will receive FT /or/ NNS alone during heel stick procedure

2.2 Design

A quasi-experimental research pre-posttest design was utilized to achieve the aim of the current study.

2.3 Setting

The study was conducted at the NICUs of both El Manial (Kaser Al Aini) and EL Monira Pediatric Hospitals that are affiliated to Cairo University. Capacity of the NICU at El Manial (Kaser Al Aini) hospital is about 64 incubators and the NICU of EL Monira Pediatric hospital is about 56 incubators. Both units provide the same protocol of care for neonates.

2.4 Participants

A purposive sample of 121 preterm infants who were admitted to both NICUs, having sucking reflex, < 37 weeks of gestation and undergoing heel stick procedure. Participants were allocated in four groups; (Control) N= 30 preterm infants, (FT) N= 31 preterm infants, (NNS) N= 30 preterm infants, and (FT combined with NNS) N=30 preterm infants. Mechanically ventilated preterm infants, with congenital anomalies, on central nervous system depressants and muscle relaxants or who underwent surgical procedures were excluded.

2.5 Data Collection Tools

The first tool is Demographic and Medical Data Form (DMDF) which was developed by the researcher. The second tool is Premature Infant Pain Profile (PIPP) Scale which has been shown to have good construct validity and moderate internal consistency (0.59–0.74) [13] The inter-rater reliability (0.93–0.96) and the intra-rater reliability (0.94–0.98) of the PIPP are excellent [14]. PIPP includes seven indicators for assessment of pain in

preterm infants, three behavioral responses (brow bulge, eye squeeze, and nasolabial furrow), two physiologic responses (heart rate and oxygen saturation), and two contextual responses (gestational age and behavioral state). Cumulative scores of both physical and behavioral indicators were summed up and total pain score were derived. The total pain score of preterm infants were interpreted as 0-6: no pain or mild pain, 7-12: moderate pain and 13-21: severe pain.

2.6 Procedure

Before conducting the study, an official permission was obtained from the directors of El Manial University Hospital and El Monira Pediatric Hospital that affiliated to Cairo University and from the heads of both NICUs, after explaining the aim and nature of the study. The researcher assessed the setting and the preterm infants according to inclusion and exclusion criteria to determine the sample of the study. The researcher explained the procedure to the parents of preterm infants as well as the benefits of interventions on the preterm infants during the heel stick procedure. Consequently, each participant was allocated by the researcher into either the control or study groups. Data was collected for each group separately until completing the required number, started with control then FT, then NNS, and finally for FT combined with NNS group. The study started at April 2023 till July 2024 when the researcher started enrollment process through daily attendance at the NICUs to recruit eligible preterm infants. Before collecting data the environment surrounding the preterm infant was prepared by reduced visual and auditory over-stimulation by decreasing brightness, alarm reductions and doors closure, infants had clean diapers and were in a quiet state before heel stick procedure. The preterm infants were connected with a calibrated monitor and pulse oximeter to monitor heart rate and oxygen saturation. The researcher assessed pain intensity for each preterm infant in all groups by using PIPP before heel stick, in which all data were collected 3 minutes without stimuli (baseline), and during heel stick procedures by co-nurse who had master degree in pain of high risk neonates and used PIPP scale previously. Every time of heel stick procedures for all the studied groups the assigned nurse exposed preterm infants' heel, cleaned it with an alcohol swab, waited for alcohol evaporate, pricked the heel using a needle, and then squeezed the heel to collect the required blood sample, after that a dry cotton ball was placed on the injured site until bleeding was ceased. Each time before contact with the preterm infant, the researcher washed hands thoroughly and wore sterile apron and face mask as aseptic precautionary measures. While the assigned nurse performed heel stick procedure, the researcher and co-nurse stood at a place where the preterm infant's face and body could be seen clearly to assess and record maximum heart rate and minimum oxygen saturation levels before and during procedure and observe the behavioral indicators (sleep/awake state, brow bulge, nasolabial furrow and eye squeeze) for each preterm infant in all studied groups.

For the control group, the researcher assessed pain intensity twice with PIPP scale (tool II) before and during the heel sticks procedure without intervention within 30 seconds after heel prick using (tool II). For the FT, researcher gently turned the preterm infant to the lateral side, positioned the arms and legs flexed, to the middle of the trunk (FT position)

for two minutes before heel stick procedure, then the assigned nurse performed the heel stick procedure for preterm infant in tucked position. The researcher retained the FT position of the preterm infant after heel stick procedure and pain intensity was assessed within 30 seconds after heel prick using (tool II) by co-nurse. As the preterm infant became comfortable (returned back to baseline physiological state and without any behavioral expressions of pain such as eye squeeze, brow bulge and nasolabial furrow) the researcher un-tucked and placed the preterm infant in pre-procedural position.

For NNS group, the researcher used a sterile pacifier for every preterm infant which was characterized by a Bisphenol-A (BPA) free, soft, flexible nipple that molded to the preterm infant's mouth that was comfortable and safe for preterm infants. The researcher put a pacifier in the preterm infant's mouth for two minutes before heel stick procedure, then the heel stick procedure done and pain intensity was assessed within 30 seconds after heel prick using tool II by co-nurse. As the preterm infant became comfortable the researcher removed the pacifier from the mouth of the preterm infant.

For FT combined with NNS group, the researcher put a sterile pacifier in the preterm infant's mouth and gently turned the preterm infant to the lateral side and positions the arms and legs flexed, to the middle of the trunk for two minutes before heel stick procedure, then the pacifier in the preterm infant's mouth was supported and kept the arms flexed with one hand while another hand supported the legs flexed and heel stick procedure was done. Pain intensity was assessed within 30 seconds after heel prick using tool II by co-nurse. As the preterm infant became comfortable the researcher removed the pacifier from the mouth, un-tucked and placed preterm infant in pre-procedural position.

2.2 Statistical Analysis

A Statistical Package for the Social Science (SPSS) program version 21 was used [15]. The collected data was tabulated, and summarized. Data was computerized and analyzed using appropriate descriptive statistics were utilized such as frequencies, mean and standard deviation. Inferential statistical tests to test the research hypotheses as the significance in standard statistical books included Student t-test, chi-square, (ANOVA) test, Post Hoc Tests, Kruskal–Wallis, Mann-Whitney U tests and Spearman test for correlation. Level of significance was set at $P < 0.05$.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Description of Participants

Figure 1 and Table 1 demonstrated that there are no statistical significance differences among study groups in relation to their mean of their gender, gestational age, age, birth weight and weight at time of enrollment ($P= 0.102, 0.400, 0.520, 0.130, \& .238$) respectively, while statistical significance differences are detected regarding their mean of Apgar score and time of last feeding ($P= .029 \& .006$) respectively.

3.2 Tests of Hypotheses

Table (2) shows that there are no statistically significant differences among total mean scores of PIPP among preterm infants in study groups before heel stick. During heel stick, PIPP mean score increased 11.57 ± 3.510 , 6.68 ± 2.344 , 9.67 ± 3.100 and 4.87 ± 2.583 in control, FT, NNS and FT combined with NNS respectively ($P=0.000$).

Table (3) indicates that FT combined with NNS, FT and NNS are effective in reducing pain compared to control group with mean difference -6.700 , -4.889 & -1.900 , ($P=.000$, $.000$ & $.045$) respectively. The same table reveals that FT combined with NNS is the most effective intervention to reduce the pain intensity among preterm infants during heel stick procedure, followed by FT intervention, followed by NNS intervention.

Table (4) reveals that there are no statistical significance differences of pain intensity among study groups before heel stick, while statistical significance differences are detected during heel stick ($P= .876$ & 0.000) respectively.

Table (5) shows that there is no correlation between total PIPP score during heel stick and preterm infant characteristics among study groups, while a positive correlation is detected between total PIPP score and time of lasting feeding in the control group only ($P= .015$).

Fig. 1: Gender of preterm infants among study groups (N=121)

Table (1): Comparison of Preterm Infants' Characteristics among the Study Groups

Preterm infant Characteristics	Groups					Total
	Control	FT	NNS	FT & NNS	P	
	Mean ± SD					
GA /wks.	31.53±1.96	32.51±2.01	32.50±1.79	33.00±2.13	0.400	32.38±2.02
Age/day	11.20 ± 9.73	14.87±10.11	14.87±14.89	14.03±7.97	0.520	13.75±10.94
Apgar score	4.80±1.955	5.42±1.478	5.73±1.363	5.87±.9	.029	5.45±1.51
Birth weight/gm.	1483.33±1.03	1588.71±1.06	1758.33±1.04	1800±1.04	.130	1657.59±1.04
Weight at time of enrollment/gm.	1516.67±1.02	1677.42±1.04	1800±1.03	1866.67±1.03	.238	1715.19±1.03
Time of last feeding/min	39.25±1.157	46.93±1.066	51±1.025	39.75±1.132	.006	44.23±1.142

Note: FT=Facilitated Tucking NNS= Non-Nutritive Sucking GA= gestational age

Wks= weeks

Table (2): Comparison of Premature Infant Pain Profile mean scores among study groups before and during heel stick

PIPP	Groups				P
	Control	FT	NNS	FT & NNS	
	Mean ± SD				
<u>Before: (0-3)</u>					
GA	1.50±.630	1.26 ±.631	1.30 ±.466	1.07±.640	.400
Behavioral state	1.93±.785	1.97±.948	1.77±.728	1.40±.894	.717
Heart rate	.07±.254	0.16±.374	.20±.484	.33±.479	.092
Oxygen saturation	0.13±.434	.00±.000	.00±.000	.00±.000	.640
Brow bulge	.03±.183	.10±.301	.20±.551	.10±.305	.353
Eye squeeze	.00±.000	.10±.301	.73±.551	.10±.305	.182
Nasolabial furrow	.00±.000	.10±.301	.20±.551	.10±.305	.182
Total PIPP(0-21)	3.53±1.502	3.68±1.194	3.90 ± 1.91	3.10±1.322	.876
<u>During: (0-3)</u>					
GA	1.50±.630	1.26±.631	1.30±.466	1.07±.640	.051
Behavioral state	1.93±.785	1.97±.948	1.77±.728	1.40±.894	.040
Heart rate	1.80±.961	1.16±.860	1.20±.847	1.00±.695	.002
Oxygen saturation	.87±1.106	0.42±0.886	.30±.596	.30±.596	.015
Brow bulge	1.83±.834	.61±.558	.73±.640	.37±.556	.000
Eye squeeze	1.80±.887	.65±.551	.70±.651	.37±.556	.000
Nasolabial furrow	1.83±.834	.61±.558	.70±.651	.37±.556	.000
Total PIPP (0-21)	11.57±3.510	6.68±2.344	9.67±3.100	4.87±2.583	.000

Note: PIPP = Premature Infant Pain Profile FT=Facilitated Tucking NNS= Non-Nutritive

Sucking GA: Gestational Age

Table (3): Comparison of Premature Infant Pain Profile mean differences among study groups during heel stick

		Dependent Variable: score				
		Games-Howell				
(I) Group	(J) Group	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Control	FT	4.889	.767	.000	2.85	6.93
	NNS	1.900	.855	.045	-.36	4.16
	FT&N.N.s	6.700	.796	.000	4.59	8.81
FT	Control	-4.889	.767	.000	-6.93	-2.85
	NNS	-2.989	.705	.001	-4.86	-1.12
	FT&N.N.s	1.811	.632	.029	.14	3.48
NNS	Control	-1.900	.855	.045	-4.16	.36
	FT	2.989	.705	.001	1.12	4.86
	FT&N.N.s	4.800	.737	.000	2.85	6.75
FT&N.N.s	Control	-6.700	.796	.000	-8.81	-4.59
	FT	-1.811	.632	.029	-3.48	-.14
	NNS	-4.800	.737	.000	-6.75	-2.85

Note: PIPP = Premature Infant Pain Profile FT=Facilitated Tucking NNS= Non-Nutritive Sucking

Table (4): Comparison of Premature Infant Pain Profile intensity among study groups before and during heel stick (N=121)

PIPP intensity	Groups								P
	Control		FT		NNS		FT & NNS		
	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%	
Before:									
No/minor : (0-<7)	29	96.7	30	96.8	28	93.3	30	100.0	.876
Moderate: (7-12)	1	3.3	1	3.2	2	6.7	0	00.0	
During:									
No/minor : (0-<7)	1	3.3	13	41.9	3	10.0	24	80.0	.000
Moderate: (7-12)	18	60.0	17	54.8	22	73.3	5	16.7	
Severe: (>12)	11	36.7	1	3.2	5	16.7	1	3.3	

Note: PIPP = Premature Infant Pain Profile FT=Facilitated Tucking NNS= Non-Nutritive Sucking

Table (5): Correlation between preterm infants' characteristics and total Premature Infant Pain Profile score during heel stick

Preterm infants Characteristics	Total PIPP score during heel stick							
	Groups							
	Control		FT		NNS		FT & NNS	
	r	p	R	p	r	p	r	P
Birth weight	-.013	.947	-.052	.781	.335	.070	-.233	.215
Weight at time of enrollment	-.145	.444	-.167	.370	.294	.115	.294	.115
APGAR score	.077	.684	-.219	.236	.093	.627	.007	.971
Age	-.186	.325	.108	.564	-.065	.732	-.073	.700
GA	-.039	.838	.148	.426	-.048	.802	-.048	.802
Time of last feeding	.439	.015	.266	.148	.189	.317	.189	.317

Note: PIPP = Premature Infant Pain Profile FT=Facilitated Tucking NNS= Non-Nutritive Sucking GA= Gestational Age

4. DISCUSSION

There is a growing interest in the effectiveness of different methods of pain management, especially in relation to non-pharmacological methods. A lot of previous studies have shown that both FT and NNS individually reduce pain responses among preterm infants during painful procedures. However, few studies have investigated the combined effect of FT and non-nutritive sucking. The current study aimed to evaluate the effect of FT and NNS on pain intensity among preterm infants during heel-stick individually and in combination.

Regarding preterm infants characteristics, the current study results demonstrated that there were no statistical significance differences among preterm infants in the four study groups in relation to their gender, age, gestational age, birth weight and weight at time of enrollment which showed homogeneity among preterm infants in studied groups.

The result of the current study showed that there was no association between PIPP mean among preterm infants undergoing painful procedure (heel stick) and preterm infants characteristics (GA, age, Apgar score, birth weight, weight at time of enrollment and time of last feeding) in FT, NNS or FT combined with NNS groups, while there was association between PIPP mean among preterm infants undergoing painful procedure (heel stick) and time of last time of feeding in the control group only and no association for other preterm infants characteristics was detected (P= .015).

This result disagrees with [16] who reported that there was no association between level of pain among preterm infants undergoing painful procedure and time of last feeding in

control and intervention group. From the researcher point of view, this association may be related to positive effect of interventions more than the control group. While, this finding is supported with the same study [16] who reported that there was no association of (GA, weight and Apgar score) with their mean score level of pain among preterm infants undergoing painful procedure in control and intervention group.

Also, this result agrees with [17] who reported that, postnatal age was not associated with the PIPP scores, while this result contradicts with the same study [17] who reported that there was a significant association between the total scores of infants on the PIPP and GA and [18] who reported that Neonates' GA at time of birth influenced their pain scores. In contrast, this finding isn't in the same line of the study was carried out by [19] which highlighted that total facial responses during the lance were positively related to, APGAR at 1 minute, eye squeeze during the lance were positively related to, APGAR at 1 minute, HR variability was negatively correlated with Apgar at 1 minute and post-heel lance, stress cues were negatively correlated with Apgar at 1 minute.

Also, this result isn't in the same line with [20] who reported that Apgar scores at 1 min were negatively associated with behavioral pain scores, while Apgar scores at 5 min after birth were positively associated with behavioral pain scores.

The current study showed that FT intervention was an effective method of pain management in preterm infants more than NNS method and routine care (no intervention). This finding agree with a systematic review done by [9] under title of "The effect of FT position during painful procedure in pain management of preterm infants in neonatal intensive care unit: a systematic review and meta-analysis" which showed that FT position was an effective method of pain management in preterm infants than routine care. Also, [21] concluded that FT is a safe and effective non-pharmacological pain reduction strategy.

Also, there are previous studies which supported this finding such as [22] which revealed that FT resulted in lower pain scores and better comfort levels in the intervention group during repeated measurements, with a lasting effect 15 minutes post-heel stick. ANOVA results highlighted large clinical significance ($p < 0.001$) and concluded "FT" effectively reduces newborns' pain and improves their comfort during heel-stick blood sampling, [23] which reported that neonates in the experimental group had significantly lesser pain (less Neonatal Infant Pain Scale score) than the neonates in the control group ($P < 0.001$) which confirmed FT's effectiveness in pain reduction, [24] concluded that FT position had significantly decreasing the severity of pain compared to control group, [25] which compared to other methods like breastfeeding and kangaroo care, FT was associated with reduced crying and lower pain levels during heel stick ($p < 0.05$), [16] which demonstrated that FT led to significantly lower post-test mean pain scores in the intervention group (mean 3.2 vs. 8.3 in control, $p < 0.001$), emphasizing its statistical and clinical efficacy, and [26] revealed that FT significantly lowered Premature Infant Pain Profile (PIPP) scores across various time intervals during heel stick procedures, demonstrating its efficacy compared to procedures without FT (statistically significant at $p < 0.05$).

While, In contrast [27] have come out with different findings which contradicts with the result of the current study which showed that the mean pain intensity in each position (FT or routine position) was increased during sampling ($p=0.0001$) and after that was decreased significantly ($p=0.001$), but before, during and after sampling there was no significant difference between the two positions ($p>0.05$) which concluded that comparing neonates in the two positions; there was no significant difference in their pain intensity.

Another study supported the current study result, [28] which demonstrated that both NNS and FT effectively reduced pain scores more than routine care during heel-stick procedures but the same study contradicts with the result of the current study which concluded that NNS reduced PIPP pain scores more effectively than FT. However, FT showed broader effects not only on relieving pain, but also on enhancing infants' physiological and behavioral stability during heel-stick procedures.

The findings of the current study showed that NNS was effective in reducing pain compared to control group (no intervention). This result agrees with a Cochrane systematic review and meta-analysis of non-pharmacological interventions for newborn procedural pain demonstrated that NNS improved regulation following painful procedures in both full-term and preterm neonates, and also improved pain reactivity in full-term neonates [11].

Also, there are previous studies which supported this finding such as, [29] who conducted an RCT to study the effect of NNS on the physiological and behavioral pain response to full-term neonates during heel lancing and found that infants in the NNS had significantly lower pain scores than infants in the control group. Within this context, another randomized clinical trial was conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of NNS on preterm infants' behavioral and physiologic response to pain [30] which found that premature infants pain profile (PIPP) score was significantly lower for infants in the NNS group than that of infants in the control group during and after the heel lance.

The analgesic effect of NNS was compared against many other non-pharmacological and pharmacological analgesic strategies such as massage and oral sucrose. NNS was compared with massage and other control conditions in [31]. The researchers enrolled 90 full-term 3- to 4-days-old newborn infants and they were randomly assigned to one of the three study groups: NNS, massage, and the control groups.

Infants in the NNS group had a lower decrease in their O₂ saturation during the heel stick than infants in the massage and control groups. However, NNS was as effective as massage in reducing infants' pain score; infants in NNS group and massage group had a significantly lower level of pain on the PIPP the scale than infants in the control group. The researchers recommended applying the two interventions combined or in isolation to mitigate infants' pain.

In another randomized clinical trial the analgesic effectiveness of NNS was compared against the analgesic effect of oral sucrose [32]. The researchers included 156 full-term infants who received vitamin K IM injections. Infants were randomized to one of the three study groups: NNS, oral sucrose, and routine care groups.

The researchers found that NNS was as effective as oral sucrose in controlling infants' pain; the pain score on Neonatal Facial Coding System, the heart rate, and respiratory rate of infants in NNS group and oral sucrose group were significantly lower than that of infants in the routine care group. While this finding contradicts with [33] who studied "Effect of Non-Pharmacological Methods in the Reduction of Neonatal Pain: Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis" concluded that nonnutritive sucking is not effective in reducing neonatal pain derived from invasive procedures such as heel prick.

Concerning combination of FT and NNS, the current study findings revealed that is more effective in reducing the pain intensity among preterm infants during heel stick procedure compared to FT and NNS alone, followed with FT, followed with NNS. This result agrees with a systematic review [21] which concluded that combined non-pharmacological pain reduction methods are more effective than isolated methods. Also, this result is in the same line with [34] that investigated effects of combined use of non-nutritive sucking, oral sucrose, and facilitated tucking on infant behavioral states across heel-stick procedures and reported that combined treatments of non-nutritive sucking, and facilitated tucking more effectively reduced infants' fussing or crying than routine care across heel stick procedures.

Also, [35] that studied development of a traumatic heel-stick procedure by combined treatment with non-nutritive sucking, oral sucrose, and facilitated tucking and stated that the combined use of non-pharmacological interventions (non-nutritive sucking and facilitated tucking) effectively reduced the frequencies of infants' withdrawal behaviors, i.e. grimace and limb and trunk extension or squirming. Similarly [34] which concluded that FT that was added to the combined breast milk and NNS was more effective in reducing moderate to severe preterm infants' pain during heel stick procedures than the routine provided care.

While, this result contradicts with [12] a randomized clinical trial which reported that adding FT to NNS did not significantly add to the analgesic effectiveness of NNS alone during heel pricking procedures, however, adding FT was effective in reducing the pain recovery time after the procedure.

From the current study findings, the postulated hypotheses are accepted and these findings will be added to the growing body of literature by indicating that FT combined with NNS appears too superior to FT or NNS individually and to routine care (no intervention) on pain management during painful procedures.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

It can concluded from the current study that combination of FT with non- nutritive sucking followed by FT and NNS were effectively reduced pain scores more than routine care during heel-stick procedures. Combination of FT with non- nutritive sucking is the most effective intervention that reduced PIPP pain scores among preterm infants during heel stick procedure. Replication on a large group of sample to validate the findings and to make generalizations is recommended and it can be taking up on other procedural pain

that occur in NICU. Further investigations into the description of FT and combined FT with NNS variables (e.g., frequency, duration) are recommended to enhance the understanding of the real positive effect of them on pain intensity.

6. LIMITATIONS

There were not limitations in the current study.

7. ABBREVIATIONS

WHO	World Health Organization
NICU	Neonatal Intensive Care Unit
IM	intramuscular
IASP	International Association for the Study of Pain
FT	FT
NNS	Non-Nutritive Sucking
D MDF	Demographic and Medical Data Form
PIPP	Premature Infant Pain Profile
BPA	Bisphenol- A
SPSS	Statistical Package for the Social Science

8. DECLARATIONS

8.1 Ethical Considerations

This study was part of a Doctorate thesis; a primary approval was attained from the research ethical committee in the Faculty of Nursing, Cairo University. All preterm infants' parents who participated in the study were informed about the aim, procedure, benefits, and nature of the study and the written consent was obtained by the researcher from parents. The researcher emphasized that participation in the study was voluntary, and parents can refuse to participate in the study without any reason and obtained data was only used for the research purpose. The confidentiality of information was assured and the parents had the right to withdraw from the study at any time during the study without any effect on the care provided to their neonates.

8.2 Availability of data and materials

The data that support the findings of this trial are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

8.3 Competing Interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

8.4 Funding

This study received no specific grant from any funding agency in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

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